

ASSESSMENT OF SELF-SUFFICIENCY AMONG SOUTH ZONE INTER UNIVERSITY PLAYERS OF DIFFERENT GAMES

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Abstract:

The aim of the study was to comparative study on self-sufficiency among the South Zone Inter University players of various games namely basketball, volleyball and handball. To achieve the purpose, 15 players from all the three games (N = 45) were selected from South Zone Inter University tournaments. The first group with basketball players, the second group with volleyball players and the third group with handball players. Self-sufficiency questionnaire was used to collect data from the players. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) statistical technique was used analyse the data. The results of the study clearly showed that there was significant difference among players of various games in self-sufficiency. The study also revealed that basketball players had more self-sufficiency than volleyball and handball players.

Key Words: Basketball, Volleyball, Handball, Self-Sufficiency

1. Introduction:

Sports and games play a vital role in developing worldwide sympathetic as well as brother hood. A sport is also one of the factors rising state personality. A country's feature is depending on the health of the people. The prime object of bodily teaching is to help individual achieve the maximum mental, physical and social fitness of which he is capable.

Sport is one of the world's most powerful communication tools due to its near universal appeal, its convening power and its many positive associations. (Gopalakrishnan R. W., 2012).

Sports provide healthy and socially acceptable opportunities for the people and nations to compete against each other thereby touching heights of excellence of human endeavor and attainment. (Hardayal Singh, 1991).

Personality is the sum of activities that can be discovered by actual observations over a long enough period of time to give reliable information. Personality is a dynamic organization within the individual of those Psycho-physical systems that determine his unique adjustment to his environment.

Personality is made up of a number of elements such as personal appearance, physical constitution, knowledge experience, intelligence, character, habits, temperament, attitudes and beliefs. (Geetha Mathew, 1997).

Sports are a dynamic social force in our culture. Sports have become an important part of the culture of the nations throughout the world. (Uppal, A.K, et. al., 2004)

Many sports psychologists have studied the relationship between personality and sports performance. Various researchers have reported that athletes or players are more independent, objective, self-confident, competitive, outgoing or extroverted and less anxious than nonathletes. (Wuest, Deboran A, et. al., 1992).

Self-sufficiency is overlapping states of being in which a person or organization needs little or no help from, or interaction with, others. Self-sufficiency entails the self being enough and a self-sustaining entity can maintain self-sufficiency indefinitely.

2. Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to comparative study on self-sufficiency among the South Zone Inter University players of various games namely basketball, volleyball and handball. To achieve the aim of the study, forty-five players were selected randomly from various games namely basketball, volleyball and handball from the South Zone Inter University tournaments. 15 players of each game made as one group and all the three groups were given the Self-sufficiency questionnaire to assess their self- sufficiency quality. The data which were collected from subjects were treated statistically. To find out the significance differences in self-sufficiency among the players of various games, one way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used as a statistical technique. To find out the paired mean differences, the Scheffe's s post test was used. The level of confidence was fixed at 0.05 level to test the significance.

3. Results and Discussion:

On the basis of statistical treatment on the collected data, the results on self- sufficiency presented in the below tables. This part deals with the analysis of data collected from the samples under study. This research was to compare the self- sufficiency among the South Zone Inter University players of various games namely basketball, volleyball and handball. To achieve the purpose of this study, 15 basketball players, 15 volleyball players and 15 handball players from South Zone Inter University tournament were selected. The subjects were

selected at random; the selected subjects were evaluated on their self-sufficiency based on Self-sufficiency Questionnaire.

Table 1: Showing the Analysis of Variance on the Means obtained in from Different game players represented South Zone Inter University Tournaments in the Personality trait self-Sufficiency

	Basketball Group	Volleyball Group	Handball Group	Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean squares	Obtained F-ratio
Mean	14.53	10.93	11.00	B	127.24	2	63.62	108.33*
				W	24.67	42	0.59	

Table F-ratio at 0.05 level of confidence for 2 and 41 (df) = 3.22,
 2 and 42 df = 3.22

* : Significant

Table I shows the analyzed data on self-sufficient. The test means of self-sufficiency were 14.53 for basketball group, 10.93 for volleyball group and 11.00 for handball group. The obtained F-ratio 108.33 was greater than the table F-ratio 3.22. Hence the test was insignificant at 0.05 level of confidence for the degrees of freedom 2 and 42.

Since there were significant differences among the players of different games of South Zone Inter University, Scheffe's post hoc test was used to find out the paired mean differences among the groups, which is presented in Table II.

Table 2: Showing Means, Mean Differences and the Required Value of Scheffe's Confidence Interval

Basketball Group	Volleyball Group	Handball Group	Mean Difference (MD)	C.I Value
14.53	10.93		3.6*	0.70
14.53		11.00	3.53*	
	10.93	11.00	0.07	

*: Significant

Table II shows the scheffe's post-hoc test of mean difference of self-sufficiency for different groups. The differences between the basketball group and volleyball group was 3.6, basketball group and handball group was 3.53 and volleyball group and handball group was 0.07. Hence, the first and second group comparisons were significant and third comparison was insignificant.

The analysis of variance of self-sufficiency indicated that basketball players had more self-sufficiency than volleyball and handball players.

4. Conclusion:

Within the limitations and delimitations of this study, the following conclusions were arrived at:

- It was concluded that basketball players had more self-sufficiency than volleyball and handball players.
- It was concluded that volleyball and handball players had less self-sufficiency while compare to basketball players.

5. References:

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